

[研究文章 Research Article]

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Amendment for the Occurrences of *Calicnemia eximia* (Selys, 1863) and *Orthetrum testaceum* (Burmeister, 1839) in Taiwan (Odonata: Platynemididae, Libellulidae)

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Abstract: The status of *Calicnemia eximia* (Selys, 1863) and *Orthetrum testaceum* (Burmeister, 1839) in Taiwan is reviewed based on the examination of voucher specimens and distributional patterns. Both species are considered doubtfully recorded from Taiwan and are therefore excluded from the Taiwanese fauna.

Key words: Oriental region, damselfly, dragonfly, fauna, doubtful records

Introduction

According to Tsou (2023), the Odonata fauna in Taiwan comprises around 160 species. However, the exact number of species is still unclear because new records of species (Ma et al. 2022; Hu et al. 2023; Lee et al. 2024), corrections of misidentifications (Hu et al. 2021; Hu & Futahashi 2023; Yeh 2023; Yeh & Hu 2023), and taxonomic changes (Kosterin 2023; Lin 2023; Schneider et al. 2023) published in the last few years indicate that the fauna is still not fully understood. Among the recorded species, the records of *Calicnemia eximia* (Selys, 1863) and *Orthetrum testaceum* (Burmeister, 1839) are highly doubtful as no further records have been published since the first reports (Fraser 1936; Lieftinck et al. 1984). The present study investigates the status of these two doubtful species through voucher specimen and distribution patterns in Taiwan.

Materials and methods

The examined specimen of *C. eximia* was deposited at the Natural History Museum of Denmark (NHMD). The voucher specimen of *O. testaceum* was not examined, as the original report did not include any specimen information (Fraser 1936). The photos were taken using a Canon EOS R7 with a Canon RF 100mm F2.8L Macro IS USM lens. The images were stacked using Helicon Focus 8 and subsequently edited in Adobe Photoshop CS5 to remove the background. The data used to establish the distributional patterns of both species were gathered from published references and all iNaturalist (<https://www.inaturalist.org/>) records of *C. eximia* and *O. testaceum* as of January 1, 2025. The iNaturalist dataset includes 167 records of *C. eximia* and 3,313 records of *O. testaceum*.

Results and discussion

美姿琵琶

Calicnemia eximia (Selys, 1863)

(Figs 1–2)

Material examined: 1 male, Syd-Formosa 10-10-02. / Coll. Esben-Petersen / *Calicnemia eximia* Selys det. MA Lieftinck 1981 / I do not know the species and am not able now to make out its true position F. Ris (NHMD).

Comments: Lieftinck et al. (1984) first reported *C. eximia* from Taiwan based solely on one specimen deposited at NHMD, but no further collecting records have been published thereafter. The voucher specimen is part of the collection of Esben-Petersen, labelled as “Syd-Formosa,” meaning southern Taiwan. However, Esben-Petersen apparently never visited Taiwan, as most of his work on Taiwanese fauna relied on the collection of Hans Sauter (e.g., Esben-Petersen 1912, 1913). The labels also do not resemble typical labels written by Sauter, which usually include a more specific locality name such as “Anping,” are printed rather than handwritten, and bear his name. This raises doubt about the origin of the specimen. Additionally, according to both published references and iNaturalist data, *C. eximia* is widespread in the Indo-Chinese region, with its easternmost population recorded in Guangxi, China (Zhang 2019). The wide distributional gap between Guangxi and Taiwan further suggests that the Taiwanese record is dubious. Based on the atypical labeling and widely separated distributional pattern, I hence exclude this species from the Taiwanese fauna.

Figure 1. The voucher specimen for the record of *Calicnemia eximia* (Selys, 1863) from Taiwan. A, Dorsal habitus; B, abdomen, in dorsal view; C, abdomen, in lateral view. Scale bar: 3 mm.

赭黃蜻蛉

Orthetrum testaceum (Burmeister, 1839)

Comments: Fraser (1936) first listed *O. testaceum* from Taiwan and stated that the species occurred from Burma to the Philippines and Formosa (Taiwan). However, no specimen was mentioned in Fraser (1936), and there have been no additional records since his publication. The species is widespread in the Oriental region but the only Chinese records, from Sichuan and Yunnan (Wilson 2011), remain dubious and are distant from Taiwan. Although the species is found in the Philippines, which is geographically close to Taiwan, its population appears to be restricted to areas south of central Luzon, based on iNaturalist data. Given the lack of a voucher specimen and the distributional pattern, I exclude this species from the Taiwanese fauna.

Figure 2. The voucher specimen for the record of *Calicnemia eximia* (Selys, 1863) from Taiwan. A, head, in dorsal view; B, head, in frontal view; C, habitus, in lateral view; D, the attached labels. Scale bar: A–B: 1 mm; C: 3 mm.

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臺灣產美姿琵琶與赭黃蜻蜓分布紀錄之訂正（蜻蜓目：琵琶科、蜻蜓科）

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摘要: 本文透過標本檢查與分佈模式重新探討美姿琵琶 (*Calicnemia eximia*) 與赭黃蜻蜓 (*Orthetrum testaceum*) 在臺灣之分布紀錄，這兩個物種都被認為是可疑紀錄，隨後排除在臺灣的動物相之外。

關鍵字: 東方區、豆娘、蜻蜓、動物相、可疑紀錄